

A STORY-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *Language learning through different methods and approaches make this challenge easier and more interesting. There are several methods in language teaching can be highly effective in engaging learners and facilitating language acquisition. One of them is story-based approach, which can be employed to teach academic subjects by introducing concepts and ideas through narratives and this allows students to connect with the material on a personal level and understand its relevance and application in real-life situations. In this article the benefits of the usage of story-based approach in enhancing language learning are discussed.*

Key words: *story-based approach, communication skill, language acquisition, narrative, contextualization, storytelling, role-playing.*

СЮЖЕТНЫЙ ПОДХОД В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ.

Аннотация. *Изучение языка с помощью различных методов и подходов делает эту задачу проще и интереснее. Существует несколько методов преподавания языка, которые могут быть очень эффективными для вовлечения учащихся и облегчения овладения языком. Одним из них является подход, основанный на рассказах, который можно использовать при преподавании академических предметов путем представления концепций и идей через повествования, что позволяет учащимся познакомиться с материалом на личном уровне и понять его актуальность и применение в реальных жизненных ситуациях. В этой статье обсуждаются преимущества использования сюжетного подхода для улучшения изучения языка.*

Ключевые слова: *сюжетный подход, коммуникативные навыки, овладение языком, повествование, контекстуализация, рассказывание историй, ролевая игра.*

INTRODUCTION.

As stated in their book "Story-based Language Teaching," Harmer & Puchta (2018) assert that stories inspire students and foster a unique learning environment that helps them relate more deeply to the material being covered in class and the new vocabulary. Stories likely have an effect on students' retention of the lesson because of this same emotional connection. A story-based approach, sometimes referred to as a narrative approach, is a framework or method that uses stories to communicate ideas in a variety of contexts, such as marketing, education, and counseling. A story-based approach uses storytelling components to engage and connect with the audience more deeply than straight or didactic information presentation. By presenting concepts and ideas through narratives, a story-based approach can be used in the educational setting to teach academic subjects. This makes it possible for pupils to relate to the information on a personal level and comprehend how applicable it is to real-world circumstances.

There have been several researchers, who have studied the story-based approach in various fields. Walter Fisher is a communication scholar who created the narrative paradigm, which holds that stories influence our thoughts and behaviors and that people are essentially storytellers. His

contributions have had a significant impact on communication studies. The other scholar is Jerome Bruner, who is a psychologist who has written extensively on the use of narrative and story in education and learning. He argues that storytelling is a fundamental part of human experience and can be used to enhance learning and understanding. While, James Geary argues that storytelling is a powerful tool for persuasion and communication.

METHODS. The use of a story-based approach in teaching language is a method that involves using stories to engage learners and facilitate language acquisition. Instead of focusing solely on grammar rules and vocabulary lists, this approach encourages learners to understand and use the language in a more meaningful and contextualized way.

Here are a few benefits of using a story-based approach in language teaching:

1. **Comprehension:** Stories help improve reading or listening comprehension skills. Learners can listen to or read stories that are at their level of proficiency, enabling them to understand and follow the narrative.
2. **Contextualization:** Stories provide a rich context for language learning. They offer real-life situations, characters, and settings, which help learners understand how language is used in different contexts.
3. **Acquiring vocabulary and grammar:** Learners are introduced to a variety of vocabulary words and grammatical structures in a context that makes sense to them through stories. This can improve their ability to retain and comprehend new information.
4. **Cultural understanding:** Stories often reflect the cultural aspects of the language being taught. By using stories, learners can gain insight into the customs, traditions, and values of the target language culture.

RESULTS. Thus, how may language instruction use a story-based approach? Here are some suggestions:

1. **Reading or listening comprehension:** Teachers can select or create stories suitable for the language level of the learners. After reading or listening to the story, various comprehension activities can be done to reinforce language skills.
2. **Storytelling:** Teachers can also tell stories to the learners, using gestures, props, and visuals to enhance understanding. Learners can then retell the story or even create their own versions.
3. **Role-playing:** Learners can act out scenes from a story, taking on the roles of the characters. This activity encourages speaking skills, creativity, and language confidence.
4. **Writing activities:** Learners can write their own stories, either as a continuation of an existing story or as an entirely new piece. This fosters imagination, writing skills, and language production.

In general, using a story-based approach in language instruction can greatly improve student engagement and speed up language learning. It provides a contextualized and relevant learning experience, which has several advantages.

DISCUSSION. A good narrative is loved by all, but especially by kids. Since stories are already familiar to them in their native tongue, using stories in the English classroom is a useful strategy for introducing new vocabulary in a context that will stick in their minds. Children benefit from stories by being exposed to more English and by developing their own vocabulary.

Stories work well as teaching aids because they are interesting, convincing, and remembered. Because stories deal with human-like experience, which we tend to view as a real and credible source of knowledge, they are believable.

The story-based approach in teaching foreign language involves using stories and narratives as the central component of language instruction. In order to apply this approach in teaching, first of all, age-appropriate stories should be selected, because they may be interesting and relevant to the students. The stories can be traditional folk tales, modern literature, or even original stories created by you or your students. The next step is pre-teaching vocabulary and language structures. This will help students understand the story better and reduce their reliance on translations. Then, reading and discussion of the story aloud, emphasizing pronunciation, intonation, and expression, visual aids, gestures, and facial expressions can be used to enhance comprehension. After that, language activities based on the story. These activities can include vocabulary exercises, grammar practice, role-plays, storytelling, and creative writing. The last steps are Extension of the story and using the language in context. Students can extend the story by creating alternate endings, writing sequels or prequels, or adapting the story into different formats (e.g., a play, a comic strip, or a video).

CONCLUSION.

In summary, the story-based approach in teaching foreign languages promotes language acquisition through meaningful and engaging contexts. It allows students to connect emotionally with the language and develop their language skills in a natural and holistic way, if the approach is used correctly.

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